

Prevalence of depression and suicidal ideation among bereaved medical students University of Khartoum in 2018

Yasir A. Hamed⁽¹⁾, Kamil M. A. Shaaban⁽²⁾

***Correspondence to:**

Faculty of medicine,

University of Khartoum,

Khartoum state, Sudan

Phone No.:090157889

Email:Yo.chazz@yahoo.com

¹ MBBS Faculty of medicine, Teaching Assistant in department of psychiatry University of Khartoum, Khartoum state, Sudan

² The supervisor of the research .Associated Professor, Community Physician and Psychiatrist, Faculty of medicine, University of Khartoum, Khartoum state, Sudan

i. Abstract:

Background: In our life absolutely we will be facing struggles and stressful events and one of the most traumatic events is the loss of a significant person (bereavement) and the issue arise from that this experience in young adults usually tend to be new and they don't know how to deal with it properly.

Bereavement by itself is a normal reaction that takes it time and go (resolved bereavement) but sometimes people tend to stuck in this reaction (unresolved bereavement) and it gets complicated by the feeling of anger and guilt specially if the death of the diseased was sudden . And this kind of unresolved bereavement is one of the risk factor not only for depression but also for suicidal ideation.

Objectives: to determine the prevalence of Depression among bereaved medical students in the recent two years in University of Khartoum in 2018.

Method: this study is a cross sectional study.46 Medical students age 18-24 years in University of Khartoum that have a bereavement experience in the period between 2016 and 2018 have been recruited by using a Google form send to every batch social secretary and filled the bereavement and PHQ-9 questionnaires.

Results: The results show that 38 participants (82.6%) are having unresolved bereavement and 8 participants (17.4%) had a bereavement experience but it have been resolved. 29 participants (63%) have been found to have depression and 17 participants (37%) have been found not to have depression. 26 participants (56.52%) have shown no evidence of suicidal ideation, 20 participants (43.48%) have shown evidence of suicidal ideation. No evidence have been found suggesting association between gender and unresolved bereavement (Fischer exact test was found 0.700).Strong evidence have been found suggesting association between unresolved bereavement and depression (Fischer exact test was found less than 0.001). Strong evidence have been found suggesting correlation between Suicidal ideation and severity of depression (Spearman's rho was found 0.800 and p value was less than 0.001). Strong evidence has been found suggesting association between suicidal ideation, depression severity and the need of more professional help. 33 participants (71.7%) stated that they need more professional help.

Conclusion: In conclusion we have shown that the significant loss of a dear person in these subjects tends to have unresolved bereavement with depression, and even severe depression, associated with suicidal ideation. And they need more help to return to internal equilibrium or merely to adapt.

1. Introduction:

1.1 Background:-

In our life absolutely we will be facing struggles and stressful events and one of the most traumatic events is the loss of a significant person (bereavement) and the issue arises from that this experience in young adults usually tend to be new and they don't know how to deal with it properly.

Bereavement by itself is a normal reaction that takes its time and goes (resolved bereavement) but sometimes people tend to get stuck in this reaction (unresolved bereavement) and it gets complicated by the feeling of anger and guilt especially if the death of the diseased was sudden. And this kind of unresolved bereavement is one of the risk factors not only for depression but also for suicidal ideation. ⁽¹⁾

While it is becoming increasingly clear that mood disorders tend to be chronic, intermittent and/or recurrent conditions with different manifestations over time, little is known of the variability or course of mood disorders that are associated with severe psychosocial stress ⁽²⁾. And as mental health is now included in the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) so it is becoming more important for the non-medicals to know it and to help in make it better and better.

Unipolar depressive disorder in adolescence is common worldwide but often unrecognized. The incidence, notably in girls, rises sharply after puberty and, by the end of adolescence, the 1 year prevalence rate exceeds 4. The burden is highest in low-income and middle-income countries. ⁽³⁾

Functional brain changes have been identified in adults but less consistently in adolescent depression. There is a clear trend that despite a growing body of research into the neurobiological correlates of depression, the evidence in children and adolescents is limited to the extent that no firm conclusions may yet be drawn. ⁽⁴⁾

The impact of the loss of someone close depended to an important extent on the young person's perception of how the loss had changed their lives. Most adolescents did not feel the need for professional services. Those who did use these services had higher levels of depressive symptoms, suggesting that service use was likely to have been appropriate.

Early bereavement and loss have been prominent themes in many models of psychopathology (Freud, 1917; Bowlby, 1969) and may be vulnerability factors for mental disorder in both childhood and adult life (Black, 1998). As a result, a variety of services exist for bereaved young people (Kaplan, 1992). In planning such services, information is needed on several issues. The most important is the prevalence of bereavement among adolescents.⁽⁵⁾

In 2017 the World Health Organization released a world health report that estimated that there are 322 million cases of depressive disorder in the world and it is predicted to become the second most common disease after heart disease. Furthermore as many as 15% of all patients with major depressive disorder (MDD) ends their lives by suicide. And the lifetime suicide risk of patients with MDD is estimated at approximately 30%. Suicide ideation which is one of the main risk factors for suicide death is generally associated with depression.

1.2 Problem Statement:-

Raising the question as to how often adolescents will experience the death of someone close to them. The second question is the extent to which bereavement is associated with psychological distress and depressive symptoms. It could be that many bereaved young people remain symptom free and might not therefore require psychological help. The third question is the extent to which suicidal ideation is associated with depression severity. The fourth issue is whether bereaved youngsters feel the need for professional counseling. It could be that many of them prefer to rely on other sources of comfort and support.

1.3 Justification:-

There have been surprisingly few researches on bereaved young people worldwide (Garmezy and Masten, 1994). Most of the existent studies have been based on selected samples that have lost a parent (Weller et al., 1991; Silverman and Worden, 1992) or friend (Brent et al., 1992). So far as we know there have been no community-based studies that have assessed the whole. And we know that medical students are at high risk for depression and suicidal ideation. However, the prevalence estimates of these disorders vary between studies. And there were no study like this in University of Khartoum Faculty of Medicine among students or a recent study in Sudan.

1.4 Objectives

1.4.1 General:

To determine the prevalence of Depression among bereaved medical students in the recent two years in University of Khartoum in 2018.

1.4.2 Specific:

- To determine the socio-demographic characteristics of the students who lost a dear person.
- To assess the bereavement experience for the students who lost a dear person.
- To test for association between unresolved bereavement and depression among bereaved medical students.
- To test for association between the socio-demographic characteristics and the resolve of bereavement among bereaved students.
- To test for association between suicidal ideation and severity of depression among bereaved students.
- To test for association between suicidal ideation and help seeking behaviors among bereaved students.
- To test for association between depression severity and help seeking behaviors among bereaved students.
- To determine the attitude of bereaved students to professional intervention.

3 Methodology:-

3.1 Study Design:

Observational analytical cross-sectional study.

3.2 Study Setting:

The study was conducted in University of Khartoum –faculty of medicine:

Located in Al qasr Ave , Khartoum north, Khartoum state, Sudan. It is the oldest and the most prestigious faculty of medicine in Sudan. It plays a leadership role as a world-class medical school model for newer and developing medical schools, in addition to its role on the regional & international scene. It was established in February 1924 as Kitchener medical school. In September 1951 the school was linked to Khartoum University College. After independence in 1956 Khartoum university college was upgraded to Khartoum university, the medical school became a faculty of medicine and started offering the MBBS degree. N.B University College was affiliated with university of London which awarded for the graduates its graduation certificate, and contribute in establish of the curriculum & exams regulation.

The duration of teaching program is 6 years. The staff is about 201 workers who teach in 14 academic departments. The students' intake is about 350 students per year. And annually it graduates around 300 doctors.

3.3 Study population:

All medical Students University of Khartoum whom have been exposed to a bereavement experience from year 2016 till 2018.

3.3 Study Sample:

3.3.1 Sample Frame:

All medical Students University of Khartoum whom have been exposed to a bereavement experience from year 2016 till 2018.

3.3.2 Sample Size:

All medical Students University of Khartoum whom have been exposed to a bereavement experience from year 2016 till 2018. 46 students were reached with response rate of 100%.

3.4 Study Time:

The Study was conducted in the period between December 2018 and February 2019.

3.5 Data collection method:

The data was collected using a standardized, pre-tested pre-coded questionnaire on Google form format.

The questionnaire consisted of four parts:

- Sociodemographic questions.
- Bereavement questions: total of 5 questions, the first tow to know the relation to the dear person and the other was to know the time of the loss. (Using Standardized Bereavement questionnaire).⁽⁵⁾
- Help seeking behavior: total of 6 questions to asses if the bereaved students talked about the loss with a counselor or another adult in the family or a friend.
- Depression and Suicidal Ideation Questions: total of 10 questions to assess the Depression severity and the suicidal Ideation (Using the standardized PHQ-9 questionnaire).⁽¹⁵⁾

3.6 Participant recruitment:

In the faculty of medicine university of Khartoum they have a well-established social system. In every batch there is a social affairs secretary one of his functions is to know and document the losses of family member of his own batch. These secretaries of the all the 6 batches in the faculty have been contacted to reach all the students who have lost a dear person in the period of 2016 till 2018. A total of 46 students have been reached and the response rate was 100% All of students have been asked for consent and they have approved.in the Google form there was a phone Number to contact that will guide the students if they need psychiatric help near the place they live and all the data was Encrypted and to ensure confidentiality Telegram Secret chat with a self-destruct timer have been used (Telegram is an app used for social communication).

3.7 Data Analysis:

After the data have been collected it was analyzed using software package for statistical analysis (SPSS) version 25.

3.8 Ethical Concern:

The author reports no conflict of interest in this work. An approval from Community medicine, faculty of medicine, department university of Khartoum was obtained.

4 Results:

4.1 Socio-demographic characteristics of the study population:

The study included 46 participants .13 (28.3%) were males and 33 (71.7%) were females. (figure 1).The maximum age was 24 years and the minimum age was 18 years with the mean of age _of approximately 21 years and standard deviation of 1.67332.

The participants from the faculty of medicine university of Khartoum were from the whole 6 batches in the faculty and it was 1 participant from the 6th year(2.2%) , 7 participants from the 5th year(15.2%), 8 participants from the 4th year(17.4%), 10 participants from the 3rd year(21.7%), 8 participants from the 2nd year(17.4%) and 12 participants from the 1st year(26.1%).

4.1 Bereavement :

The participants share the loss of a dear person but the relationship between the participants and the person who died defer majorly and participants value them sometimes more than the others for example there is answers says “I lost my aunt she was like a mother for me “ so at the end they share the loss of someone who made an impact in their lives . The highest was losing a Father and an Uncle 12 participants for each of them (26.1%) , followed by aunt and grandmother 6 participants for each of them (13%),4 participants have lost their mother (8.8%),then comes the loss of a sister and a best friend 2 participants for each (4.3%) lastly comes the loss of a grandfather and a brother 1 participant for each (2.2%).

4.2 Resolved and Unresolved bereavement:

The results show that 38 participants (82.6%) are having unresolved bereavement and 8 participants (17.4%) had a bereavement experience but it have been resolved.

4.3 Depression:

29 participants (63%) have been found to have depression and 17 participants (37%) have been found not to have depression.(figure 5)(cut off point is 5 in PHQ9).

4.4 Depression Severity:

When the severity of the depression of the 29 depressed participants have been assessed using PHQ9 it showed: 6 participants have been found having mild depression, 11 participants have been found having moderate depression, 8 participants have been found having moderately severe depression and 4 participants have been found having severe depression (interesting finding that one of the participants have scored 26/27).

4.5 Suicidal Ideation :

26 participants (56.52%) have shown no evidence of suicidal ideation, 20 participants (43.48%) have shown evidence of suicidal ideation.

4.6 Seeking Help Behavior:

Most participants (27 participants) tend to talk about the loss with their friends and 31 participants have never seen a university counselor or a professional in mental health. 33 participants stated that they need more professional help.

No evidence have been found suggesting association between gender and unresolved bereavement (Fischer exact test was found 0.700).

Strong evidence have been found suggesting association between unresolved bereavement and depression (Fischer exact test was found less than 0.001).

Strong evidence have been found suggesting correlation between Suicidal ideation and severity of depression (Spearman's rho was found 0.800 and p value was less than 0.001).

Strong evidence has been found suggesting association between suicidal ideation, depression severity and the need of more professional help.

(Fischer exact test was found for both associations less than 0.002).

5 Discussion:

5.1 Unresolved bereavement and Depression :

In this study we found that (82.6%) of bereaved students have unresolved bereavement. And we found evidence suggesting that loss of a parent is highly associated with depression among medical students. Our results also show that also the death of an uncle or a grandmother is also highly associated with depression this reflects the depth of how Sudanese family is connected we found that they say that the grandmother was like a mother to me or my uncle was like a father to me . As this is a cross sectional study we cannot be certain that this association is causal. It could be that there is other variables like the responsibilities of the participant in the house and how much stress he or she have to handle in the absence of the diseased. Our findings show much similarity to the findings of (Harrison & Harrington 2001) although it have been made in UK but we further

extend the research to involve the type of the bereavement is it resolved or not also we introduced Suicidal ideation and help seeking behaviors. As our findings are based on a population of adults and in (Harrison & Harrington 2001) it was based on a population of adolescents.

We did not find any association between gender and the bereavement being resolved or not. It is an interesting finding in a country like Sudan where women are thought to be more weaker towards stressful life events than men and the low rate of males that attend psychiatric clinics.

5.2 Depression Severity and Suicidal Ideation:

In this study we found evidence suggesting a high correlation between suicidal ideation and depression severity. It is well recognized that depression is one of the risk factors for Suicide and loss of a dear person is also one of the risk factors for both Suicide and depression. The result of our findings having this high correlation shows that increasing in the severity will cause increase in the suicidal ideation. In comparison to (Rotenstein 2016) we found that (43.48%) of the bereaved medical students suffer from Suicidal ideation and it is a high ratio to be compared to just (11%) in (Rotenstein 2016) but our population is already having one of the risk factors which is unresolved bereavement so it is justifiable.

5.3 Help seeking behavior and Suicidal Ideation and depression severity:

Our findings show that subjects tend to talk about the loss with friends more than talking to a professional counselor. And (71.7%) of them feel they need more professional help and they did not get it .And as a matter of fact (67.4%) of them never seen a university counselor or a university psychiatrist. In a matter of comparison to (Harrison & Harrington 2001) the students in that study did not feel the need for professional help. This disagreement between our findings may be due to the fact that our subjects students and are medical have **a good insight** that they need more help rather than adolescents that are school students in (Harrison & Harrington 2001).

Why to say a good insight?

We found evidence suggesting that the subjects that felt they need more help suffer more severe depression and suicidal ideation as this finding imply that it makes there life more difficult .

6 Conclusion:

In conclusion we have shown that the significant loss of a dear person in these subjects tends to have unresolved bereavement with depression, and even severe depression, associated with suicidal ideation. And they need more help to return to internal equilibrium.

7 Recommendations:

Professional Intervention have to be made in the period of grief to make the severity of depression and the suicidal ideation lesser, to have a clear protocol in the university to admit the bereaved student to the

psychiatric clinic for check-up because bereavement could be a new experience to the subject and don't know how to handle it.

More researches should be done to search for other variables that affect the depression such as family fragmentation after the loss. Also more research could search for the change in the academic performance of these students after the significant loss.

8 Limitations:

This study has a recall bias because some of the study subjects have been asked about events that happened two years ago (the specification of study population is to have a significant loss in the past two years).

This study is a cross sectional study so it can't be certain of the associations that it is causal.

The sample size of the study is small (46 subjects) but it is a total coverage of the whole medical students in university of Khartoum who had lost a significant person between 2016 and 2018.

10. References:-

1. Home [Internet]. RC PSYCH ROYAL COLLEGE OF PSYCHIATRISTS. 2019 [cited 4 December 2019]. Available from: <https://www.rcpsych.ac.uk>
2. Zisook S, Paulus M, Shuchter SR, Judd LL. <The many faces of depression following spousal bereavement.pdf>. 1997;45:85–95.
3. Thapar A, Collishaw S, Pine DS, Thapar AK. Depression in adolescence. *Lancet*. 2012;
4. Hirota T, Milavić G, McNicholas F, Frodl T, Skokauskas N. Depression in Children and Adolescents. In: *Systems Neuroscience in Depression*. 2016.
5. HARRISON L, HARRINGTON R. Adolescents' bereavement experiences. Prevalence, association

-
- with depressive symptoms, and use of services. *J Adolesc* [Internet]. 2001 Apr;24(2):159–69. Available from: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0140197101903793>
6. Mayo Clinic - Mayo Clinic [Internet]. *Mayoclinic.org*. 2019 [cited 4 December 2019]. Available from: <https://www.mayoclinic.org/>
 7. Lundberg T, Forinder U, Olsson M, Johan C, Årestedt K, Alvariza A. European Journal of Oncology Nursing Bereavement stressors and psychosocial well-being of young adults following the loss of a parent – A cross-sectional survey. *Eur J Oncol Nurs* [Internet]. Elsevier; 2018;35(May):33–8. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejon.2018.05.004>.
 8. Brent D, Melhem N, Donohoe M, Walker M. The Incidence and Course of Depression in Bereaved Youth 21 Months After the Loss of a Parent to Suicide, Accident, or Sudden Natural Death. *American Journal of Psychiatry*. 2009;166(7):786-794.
 9. Hawton K, Casañas i Comabella C, Haw C, Saunders K. Risk factors for suicide in individuals with depression: A systematic review. *Journal of Affective Disorders*. 2013;147(1-3):17-28.
 10. Rotenstein L, Ramos M, Torre M, Segal J, Peluso M, Guille C et al. Prevalence of Depression, Depressive Symptoms, and Suicidal Ideation Among Medical Students. *JAMA*. 2016;316(21):2214.
 11. Zhang R, Wei S, Chang M, Jiang X, Tang Y, Wang F. Dorsolateral and Ventrolateral Prefrontal Cortex Structural Changes relative to Suicidal Ideation in Patients with Depression. *Acta Neuropsychiatrica*. 2019;:1-30.
 12. Miyashita M, Aoyama M, Yoshida S, Yamada Y, Abe M, Yanagihara K et al. The distress and benefit to bereaved family members of participating in a post-bereavement survey. *Japanese Journal of Clinical Oncology*. 2017;48(2):135-143.
 13. Dueñas J, Fernández M, Morales-Vives F. What is the protective role of perceived social support and religiosity in suicidal ideation in young adults?. *The Journal of General Psychology*. 2019;:1-16.
 14. Spillane A, Matvienko-Sikar K, Larkin C, Corcoran P, Arensman E. What are the physical and psychological health effects of suicide bereavement on family members? An observational and interview mixed-methods study in Ireland. *BMJ Open*. 2018;8(1):e019472.
 15. Pfizer Inc. Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9). Pfizer. 1999;